

THE CONTENT OF THE LANGUAGE PROFESSIONAL-GNOSTIC TRAINING OF AN ENGLISH TEACHER

Ergasheva Nazokat Erkin qizi

student of the Gulistan State University, Philology faculty, English language and literature department, Gulistan, Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the research on the linguistic professional-gnostic training of English teachers and its content. Researchers' views on the term "educational content" are compared. The article offers suggestions on how to make changes to the curriculum. The results of the experiment are also described.

Keywords: professional-gnostic orientation, components of the content, speech material, methodological developments

Introduction. The professional-gnostic orientation of the process of training a future English teacher at the language faculty, as well as the professional-gnostic competence, which we have identified as the basis for the implementation of the competence of an English teacher, necessitate a deeper consideration of the problem of forming the content of teaching English to undergraduate students studying in the following specialties: "Linguodidactics", "Linguistics", "Teaching methods", "English language".

For the scientific justification of the choosing of the components of the content of the language professional-gnostic training of an English teacher, it is essential to find out what is meant by the term "content of education" The issue of determining the subject of foreign language education is a thorny one in the methodology of teaching English. This is partly owing to the fact that researchers had and continue to have differing viewpoints on the components of training content. This issue is sanctified in the works I. L. Bim, N. D. Galskova, A.D. Klimentenko, A. A. Mirolubova, E. I. Rogovo, V. V. Safonova.

Definition. The interrelated activity of the teacher (teacher's activity) and learning (student's activity) directed to the educational material or the content of the academic subject is defined as the content of teaching a foreign language. [1].

The content of the training includes the following components: domains of communicative activity, topics, circumstances, communicative and social roles; language material, design principles, operating abilities; cultural characteristics and realities of the country of the language being studied, as well as the ability to use them in different areas of speech communication; learning and

compensating (adaptive) skills that provide a culture of language acquisition and a culture of communication with native speakers.

A foreign language education's content is defined as a foreign language culture, which a student can master in the course of communicative foreign language education in the cognitive (cultural), developmental (psychological), educational (pedagogical), and educational (social) aspects as a part of the general culture of mankind." The content of education is determined by three factors: 1) the content of the educational goal-ideal; 2) the axiology of education, i.e. the values that are important for the goal; and 3) the structure of the professional teacher's activity, taking into account the specifics of the specialty [2].

The content of teaching a foreign language is regarded as one of the methodology's central problems, with the belief that it is intended to answer the question "what to teach?". They emphasize the following elements in the content of teaching a foreign language: 1) A linguistic component that incorporates both language and speech material. 2) The psychological component, which encompasses the developed skills and capacities that enable pupils to communicate using the learned language. 3) The methodological component of understanding instructional approaches [3].

In the content of teaching a foreign language, we can concentrate on the following components: knowledge; skills and abilities; topics and situations (because they "become the basis on which the learning goals are realized"); texts ("speech works on the basis of which speech skills are formed"); language concepts that are absent in the native language [4].

The following are the major steps in the design of educational content: 1) the stage of developing a list of educational competences relevant to the chosen subject; 2) the stage of identifying the objects of subject competence, taking into account their social and personal significance for students; 3. the stage at which the dynamics of subject competency development are revealed.

Teaching a foreign language to a prospective teacher is defined as "a pedagogically guided system of information, skills, and abilities, creative activity experience, and emotional-value attitude toward the world, whose integration ensures the whole development of the future foreign language teacher's personality" (V. V. Kraevsky).

In modern learning conditions, a foreign language serves as a means of learning the picture of the world and being acquainted with the values developed by other peoples. Language, at the same time, is the key to understanding the distinctiveness and originality of one's own national identity as well as the

historical achievements of representatives of other cultures. The processes of intercultural integration determine the modernization of the content of language education in Uzbekistan. However, the differing perspectives of modern scientists on the definition of the components of the content of teaching a foreign language make it impossible to construct a system of training future English teachers that is appropriate to the purposes of teaching in present conditions.[5]

The necessity to emphasize the topic of teaching English to undergraduate students was determined by the clear goals of teaching English from the perspective of the construction of professional-linguistic competence as the foundation of an English teacher's didactic activity, as well as the specific duties of an English teacher that are utilized to implement this competence on the language professional-oriented training of an English teacher in the fields of "Linguodidactics," "Linguistics," and "Teaching Methods"

The didactic, methodological, and linguistic selection principles developed by (I. L. Bim, N. D. Galskova, G. A. Kitaygorodskaya, A. A. Mirolyubov, V. V. Safonova), as well as the criteria for selecting the content of teaching English instructors constructed on their foundation, were taken into account when selecting the content of English language instruction. Professional-oriented training for foreign language teachers, in our viewpoint, is a component of English language teaching that aims to develop professional linguistic competence in English teachers.[6]

In this regard, we attempted to assess contemporary English textbooks for the third year students of a language university from the standpoint of their professional orientation to the prospective English teacher.

Teaching speech communication in English to third-year students is conducted on the basis of the curriculum, which includes educational and methodological developments, the purpose of which is "practical mastery of the system of a foreign (English) language, the formation of students' intercultural foreign language communicative competence: possession of linguistic, speech, communicative and socio-cultural knowledge, skills and abilities that allow the student to communicatively acceptable and appropriate to vary their speech behavior in situations of everyday and professional spheres of communication». Each design's name matches to the topic being explored. The following questions, which are directly related to the epistemological competency of future teacher training, are investigated within the context of a specific issue, for example, the course "Linguodidactics": 1.Linguodidactics as a general theory of

teaching English (8 hours). 2. Language personality (12 hours). 3. Language policy in the field of linguistic education (8 hours). 4. English as an object of mastering and learning (6 hours). 5. History of the development of the theory of learning (6 hours).

Content of the discipline sections:

1. Linguodidactics as a general theory of teaching English (8 hours): a) the object, subject and methods of research of linguodidactics; b) the place of linguodidactics in the knowledge system; c) the distinction between the concepts of "Linguodidactics" and "Methods of teaching English", "Didactics of a foreign language" and "linguodidactics" , etc. d) sciences related to linguodidactics: pedagogy, linguistics, psychology, physiology, cybernetics, etc. e) Linguodidactics as a methodical description of the language, linguodidactics as a new methodology for acquiring the English language, f) types of independent work, and so on.

2. Language personality (12 hours): 1. Language personality as the central category of linguodidactics. 2. The linguodidactic model. 3. The anthropological approach in linguodidactics. 4. Cognitive ability. Cognitive functions, etc.

3. Language policy in the field of linguistic education (8 hours): a) Language policy. b) The goals, objectives, and content of the language policy. c) The structure and content of modern linguistic education. d) The impact of language policy on the motivation of learning, conditions and forms of learning, etc.

4. Foreign language as an object of mastering and learning (6 hours): 1. Language acquisition and language learning. 2. A foreign language as an object of mastering and studying. 3. The process of language acquisition as an active, creative, cognitive (conscious) process. 4. Psycholinguistic mechanisms that ensure the functioning of the processes of mastering the English language. 5. Approaches to learning. Differentiated approach. Individual approach. 6. Individual psychological characteristics of students, the speed of assimilation of the material; the emotional sphere; the ability to self-esteem, etc.

5. History of the development of the theory of learning (6 hours): a) "Level model" of training. Teaching English as a means of communication and writing; b) Procedural, effective linguistics Theory of language activity; c) The process of communication as a process of social interaction based on a system of revealed social relations of jointly acting subjects; d) The role of the human factor in language, etc.

Topics for self-study: 1. Linguodidactics as a general theory of teaching English. 2. Language personality. 3. Language policy in the field of linguistic education, etc.

Teaching speech communication in English to third-year students is carried out on the basis of the curriculum, which includes educational and methodological developments, the purpose of which is "practical mastery of the system of a foreign (English) language, the formation of students' intercultural foreign language communicative competence: possession of linguistic, speech, communicative and socio-cultural knowledge, skills and abilities that allow the student to communicatively acceptable and appropriate to vary their speech behavior in situations of everyday and professional spheres of communication". The name of each development corresponds to the topic being studied. Within a certain framework, the following questions are studied: "Profession", "Home", "In the world of books", etc. (The experience of E. V. Timokhina is used). What is the essence of professional gnostic training? For each topic, it is necessary to conduct a methodological analysis and critically evaluate the educational material, manuals and teaching tools. Practically all topics are analyzed, and it is necessary to conduct an uncomplicated methodological experiment. Professional-gnostic educational-speech situations end with discussions, an abstract, essays-reasoning, conversation, debate, round table, etc. Future teachers need to learn how to observe pedagogical processes and phenomena, identify cause-and-effect relationships, and correctly use the results of a small study in their teaching activities.

The analysis of educational materials showed that the educational process does not sufficiently present educational materials that would be used to effectively prepare students - future teachers of English for professional gnostic activities. All the topics proposed for study in the educational and methodological developments are presented in general terms, the implementation of these topics in the teacher's communication with schoolchildren is not provided, the implementation of these topics at the school level is not taken into account.

The addressee, in our example, the student, in the process of communication with whom these situations will be implemented, is not taken into account when constructing educational and speech situations. We conducted observations of students - future teachers of English during their pedagogical practice in schools №2, №8, № 9, № 16 of the Gulistan city. As a result of these observations, it became clear that future English teachers are having difficulty implementing their academic knowledge and abilities in professional gnostic activities, and

that many of them are not yet ready to reach their potential as English teachers. The problem is that they are unable to adapt their lexical, grammatical, speech, and language knowledge, as well as the available language and speech material, to a specific speech level of school children. These issues develop as a result of the fact that the themes presented to undergraduate students for study at the university lack a professionally-oriented component and are not taken into account when they are implemented in English classes at school. As a result, we believe it is vital to change the curriculum themes and add professional-gnostic subtopics to them, preparing future English instructors for real-life communication problems within a certain issue. These subtopics are compiled on the basis of an analysis of modern teaching materials used in the school.

Teaching English from the perspective of focusing on professional activities, as well as the urgent need for the formation of professional-gnostic competence among future English teachers, determine the content of vocationally-oriented training of an English teacher at the language faculty .

Determination of the content of professional-gnostic training in the classroom in English at the language faculty is based on the following provisions: 1) taking into account the goals of the language professional-gnostic training of an English teacher formulated by us earlier; 2) taking into account the points of view of methodological scientists given in this paragraph on determining the content of training; 3) the need for the formation of skills that make up the professional and gnostic competence of an English teacher; 4) the implementation of the functions allocated by us as a professional pedagogical activity, in which the professional and gnostic competence of an English teacher finds its realization.

Based on this, we consider it necessary to highlight 3 aspects in the content of the linguistic professional-gnostic training of an English teacher: linguo -gnostic, psychological-gnostic and methodological -gnostic:

The linguo-gnostic aspect of the linguistic professional and gnostic training of an English teacher includes: 1. Linguistic phenomena reflecting the specifics of the implementation of the professional and pedagogical activity of an English teacher. 2. Special professionally oriented texts (newspaper and magazine publications, literary texts, interviews). 3. Topics as a reflection of the problems discussed in the 3rd year of the Faculty of Foreign Languages in the context of professional and gnostic training. Within the framework of the topics offered to students of the 3rd year, we define sub-topics of the content of professional and gnostic training, which should be the subject of consideration in the classroom in English. Each professionally oriented subtopic includes typical gnostic

situations: a) professionally oriented speech situations; b) Visual and textual materials (films, videos, pragmatic materials).

Research results. Psychological and gnostic aspect of the content of the linguistic professional -gnostic training of an English teacher consists of skills and abilities that contribute to the implementation of the professional and pedagogical functions of an English teacher, which we have identified, in which the professional and gnostic competence of the future English teacher finds its realization.

It is also important to highlight the methodological and gnostic aspect of professional and gnostic training and the formation on its basis of the professional and pedagogical activity of the future English language teacher. This aspect is aimed at teaching students the techniques of educational activities that contribute to the development of the professional and personal qualities of future English teachers, which are necessary for the successful conduct of pedagogical activities. Mastering teaching techniques is associated with the development of the following professional and gnostic skills: analyze the gnostic tasks and goals of teaching English at school; to emphasize the most significant methodological ideas; analyze modern teaching materials in the English language from the standpoint of professional and gnostic competencies; formulate the goals and objectives of an English lesson from a gnostic standpoint; draw up a lesson plan with a focus on professional gnostic skills; analyze the lessons learned; use methodological concepts and be able to explain them based on professional and gnostic competencies; use linguistic concepts and be able to explain them, relying on professional and gnostic competencies ; select educational materials based on the stages of work and psychological the pedagogical characteristics of the class; apply teaching methods, technologies, teaching and control techniques in the educational process, using gnostic competencies; explain and consolidate new educational material, based on various gnostic types of teaching.

Conclusion. Finally, it should be stated that in this article, an attempt was made to consider the general issues of the content of education to determine the content of the linguistic professional-gnostic training of an English teacher at the language faculty. For this, the category “content of education” was analyzed, and the priority competences for the professional-gnostic training of the future English language teacher were identified. All this made it possible to determine the requirements for the content of the professional and gnostic training of an English teacher and highlight its main aspects.

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